

Exploring Women's Perceptions of Home Garden Agroforestry

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SUMMARY

This study investigates the perceptions of women regarding home garden agroforestry practices in Nassarawa Local Government Area, Nigeria. A survey of 60 women across six wards was conducted using a structured questionnaire to gather data on their demographic characteristics, level of engagement, and willingness to participate in home garden agroforestry. The results show that the majority of respondents (40%) fall within the 18-25 age bracket, with 63.33% being single. Despite 68.33% of women not being engaged in home garden agroforestry, a significant 93.33% expressed willingness to participate. However, lack of space (51.67%) was identified as a major constraint hindering their involvement. This study highlights the importance of addressing socio-cultural and environmental factors to promote women's participation in home garden agroforestry, ultimately contributing to sustainable development, food security, and women's empowerment.

Keywords: Home garden agroforestry, women's perceptions, food security, women's engagement

INTRODUCTION

Home gardens, integral to agroforestry practices, play a vital role in enhancing food security, conserving biodiversity, and empowering women in rural areas (Kumar and Nair, 2004). These gardens, typically found around homesteads, serve as a hub for cultivating a diverse array of plants, including fruits, vegetables, medicinal herbs, and flowers (Kabir and Webb, 2008; Galhena, Mikunthan, and Maredia, 2013). Despite their significance, home gardens in many parts of the world, including Nigeria, remain understudied, particularly in relation to the role of women in their management and maintenance.

In Nigeria, women are pivotal in home garden management, contributing significantly to food security and family income (Abebe and Muku, 2017). However, their involvement and decision-making processes in home gardening practices are not well documented. This knowledge gap is particularly evident in Nassarawa Local Government Area (LGA) of Kano State, where women's participation in home gardening and their perceptions of these practices remain largely unexplored.

The problem of low production of orchards in homestead areas in Kano State, Nigeria, despite the availability of homestead land, underscores the need for this study (Khan Choudhury, Tarapder, Maukeeb, and Ema, 2020). The justification for this study lies in the potential of home gardens to contribute to food security, income generation, and women's empowerment (Jaenicke and Virchow, 2013; Weinberger, 2013). By examining the role of women in home garden management, this study aims to provide insights that can inform policies and programs aimed at promoting home gardening practices and enhancing the livelihoods of women in rural areas.

Gender plays a crucial role in the development and management of home gardens in rural areas. Home gardens typically rely on personal labor, with women, children, and elderly individuals being vital contributors to their management (Sthapit e al., 2004; Maroyi, 2009; Galhena et al., 2013). However, households with sufficient economic capacity may hire wage laborers to cultivate and maintain their home gardens, which can impact the composition and intensity of home garden activities (Maroyi, 2009).

Interestingly, while men often initiate the creation and development of home gardens, women typically take charge of planting and maintaining vegetables, flowers, and livestock within the garden (Howard, 2006; Akhter, 2000). Women's involvement in home gardening extends beyond mere labor; it also serves as a means of social and economic empowerment, particularly for disadvantaged groups. In backyard home gardening, women can cultivate a diverse range of fruit and medicinal plants (Talucder et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2020).

This study aims to assess the perception of women in home garden agroforestry practices in Nassarawa LGA, with specific objectives to determine the extent of women's involvement in home gardening practices and explore the relationship between selected characteristics of women and their participation in these practices. Overall, this study recommends the adoption of strategies that promote women's participation in home gardening practices, including training programs, access to credit facilities, and extension services (Berti et al., 2004; Howard, 2006; Akhter, 2000).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

The research is carried out at Nassarawa local government kano state, Nigeria which lies between longitude 110 580 370 and latitude 330 450 E (Usman et al., 2025). The research is conducted at Nassarawa LGA of Kano state; it has 11 wards (Dakata, Gama, Kawaji, Giginyu, Gwagwarwa, Gawuna, Hotoro South, Hotoro North, Kaura Goje, Tudun Murtala, Tudun Wada where 6 wards were purposely selected to explore the finding (Figure 1).

SAMPLING PROCEDURE

The sampling was a purposive sampling where 6 wards out of the 11 wards were selected to have representation of the populace. 10 respondents were selected from each ward to have a total of 60 respondents' altogether. That is 60 questionnaires were administered to collect the information.

CATEGORIES OF WOMEN TO BE TARGETED

House wives, single, widow and divorced of medium and high aged class

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The primary data to be used for the study were sourced through the use of well-structured questionnaire, which were administered to the respondents. Journals were used in collecting the secondary data.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected were presented by using descriptive statistics which includes frequency distribution and percentages. The data was analyzed using SPSS software version 20.

Figure 1: Map of Nassarawa LGA.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PERCEPTION OF WOMEN ON HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY IN THE STUDY

A total of 60 respondents were used for the study, they provided data used for the analysis. The results of the analysis of socio-economic characteristics of the assessment of perception of women on home garden agroforestry in the study area are presented as follows: The research is based on women of different category, as such only female gender was considered for the purpose of the research. That is, 100% females research.

AGE

As indicated in table 1, the results of the study revealed that, majority of the women age ranges between 18-25 years with (40%), followed by 26-35 (33.33%), followed by 26-45 (18.33%) and the least is 46 and above with 8.33%. this shows that of the respondent are young women.

MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

The results in Table 1 indicate that most of the women are single with (63.33%), and then followed by married with 36.67%.

The recent findings is contrary to that of Gabiso, Abebe, and Tefer, (2015) that showed that most of the respondents were middle aged from 30-50 years while the remaining 11.11% of them are from 51-60 years and that most of all the respondents owned home gardens. The contradiction could be as a result of the culture variations as mostly in the northern part of the Nigeria, women at home are not allowed to engage in talks with a stranger and also the younger women (single) are more socially oriented and would like to spend time with nature than the elderly.

Table 1: The Age Structure of Respondents in the Study Area

Age group (years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25	24	40
26-35	20	33.33
26-45	11	18.33
46-above	5	8.33
Total	60	100
Distribution of the Respondents by Marital Status		
Marital status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Married	22	36.67
Single	38	63.33
Widow	0	0
Divorced	0	0
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

RESPONDENTS PERCEPTION ON HOME GARDEN

Respondents level of engagement on home garden agroforestry

Table 2 indicates the level of women engagement in home garden agroforestry where most of the women are not engaged in home garden agroforestry activities with (68.33%) and 23.33% of the women are engaged in home gardening agroforestry while 8.33% are well engaged in the activity.

This result is not in line with the findings of (Ogunlela and Mukhtar, 2009; Umar, Chidozie, Mohammed and Tauheed 2018) that reported that women are greatly involved in crop production activities. This low level of engagement could be due several factors such as lack of space, management skills, production inputs and knowledge of cultivation.

Table 2: How familiar are you with the concept of home garden agroforestry?

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Well engaged	5	8.33
Engaged	14	23.33
Not engaged	41	68.33
Others	0	0
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

FACTORS THAT MOTIVATE WOMEN TO ENGAGE IN HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY

Table 2 below shows the factors that can motivate women to participate in home garden agroforestry practice where 45% of the respondents as majority chose knowledge as the factor that can stimulate their engagement, while 35% chose food security as the reason that can motivate them and also 13.33% chose nature conservation as what can force their performance and lastly 6.67% falls under other options like recreation and aesthetic value.

Table 2: What do you think can motivate women to participate in home garden agroforestry activities?

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Knowledge	27	45
Nature conservation	8	13.33
Food security	21	35
Others	4	6.67
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

PERCEPTION OF WOMEN ON THE BENEFITS OF HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY

Table 3 present the benefits that can be gotten from practicing home garden agroforestry, where most of the respondent select food as the benefit that can be obtained which account 63.33% of the respondents and 28.33% select income as the major benefits to be obtained and 8.33% goes for recreation.

The crucial role of women in ensuring food security is further underscored by their significant contributions to the three key components of food security: food production, accessibility, and utilization (World Bank, 2009). This recent investigation re-affirms the findings of Harrison (2016), who noted that the primary motivations for establishing home gardens are to enhance food security and nutritional well-being. Additionally, this findings showed other benefits derived from the system as perceived by the respondent's such as soil and water conservation, climate change mitigation and source of income.

THE ROLE OF HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY TOWARDS NATURAL RESOURCE CONSERVATION

Table 3 present the role of home garden agroforestry towards natural resource conservation. 73.33% of the women chose all the options as majority, followed by 10% for water conservation and biodiversity conservation and 6.67% select soil conservation as the least selected option.

PERCEPTION OF WOMEN ON HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Table 3 presents the view of women in the study area on home garden agroforestry towards sustainable development where 70% goes for all of the options, 13.33% are of food security and environmental sustainability and the least with 3.33% are of climate change mitigation choice.

Table 3: What benefits do you think can be obtained from practicing home garden agroforestry?

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Income	17	28.33
Food	38	63.33
Recreation	5	8.33
Others	0	0
Total	60	100
What role do you think home garden agroforestry can play in natural resource conservation		
Water conservation	6	10
Soil conservation	4	6.67
Biodiversity conservation	6	10
All of the above	44	73.33
Total	60	100
How do you see home garden agroforestry towards sustainable development?		
Climate change mitigation	2	3.33
Food security	8	13.33
Environmental sustainability	8	13.33
All of the above	42	70
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

PERCEPTION OF WOMEN ON THE CHALLENGES THAT HINDER THEM FROM PRACTICING HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY

Table 4 below showed the challenges that hinder women from practicing home garden agroforestry, where most of the women of about 51.67% goes for lack of space as the issue that stop women from the practice, while 36.67% select lack of support from government and organizations as the problem that stop women from practicing home garden agroforestry and 10% goes for lack of awareness while 1.677% thought of inadequate inputs.

Table 4: What do you think are the challenges or barriers that can hinder women from practicing home garden agroforestry?

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Awareness	6	10
Lack of space	31	51.67
Support	22	36.67
Others	1	1.66
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS AND WOMEN'S INVOLVEMENT IN HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY
FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE WOMEN PARTICIPATION ON HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY

Table 5 below indicated if there is any social or cultural factor that can influence women participation on home garden agroforestry. 90% are of the option no, that is there is no any social or cultural factor that stop their participation and only 10% have some social or cultural factor that stop their participation like the level of practice in the society is minimal and usually influence them.

Table 5: Are there any social or cultural factors that influence your participation in home garden agroforestry?

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	6	10
No	54	90
Total	60	100
Have you ever engage in home garden agroforestry practices?		
Yes	26	43.33
No	34	56.67
Total	60	100
Are you willing to engage in home garden agroforestry practices?		
Yes	56	93.33
No	4	6.67
Total	60	100
Are there any specific trees or plants that you prefer to include in your home garden agroforestry system?		
Yes	50	83.33
No	10	16.67
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

PERCEPTION OF WOMEN ON HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY INVOLVEMENT

Table 5 showed whether the women in the study area have ever engaged in home garden agroforestry practice or not. Majority with 56.67% have not engage in the practice and 43.33% have engaged in the practice.

WILLINGNESS OF WOMEN ON HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY PRACTICE

Table 5 below shows the willingness of the respondents on home garden agroforestry where 93.33% are willing to engage in the practice and only 6.67% have not developed interest.

RESPONDENTS PERCEPTION ON SPECIFIC TREES/PLANTS TO BE INCLUDED IN HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY PRACTICES

Table 5 below indicates the respondents view on whether if there are some specific trees or plants that they would prefer to include in while practicing home gardening agroforestry where 83.33% are having specific trees/plants that they prefer such as guava tree, mango tree, *Moringa* tree, lemon grass, papaya and banana while 16.67% do not have specification.

This finding suggest that home garden agroforestry has the potential to be a widely accepted and beneficial practice among the respondents, but that social and cultural factors may need to be addressed in order to fully realize this potential.

RESPONDENTS PERCEPTION ON THE TREES/PLANTS THAT CAN BE CULTIVATED IN HOME GARDEN AGROFORESTRY PRACTICES

Table 6 provides options for the trees/plants that women in the study area prefer to cultivate. 73.33% goes for *Moringa*, 16.67% goes for fruit trees, 8.33% goes for papaya, mango and Indian almond tree and 1.67% goes for other option such as lemon grass, guava and banana. The dominance of *Moringa* and vegetables could be attributed to the high nutritional and medicinal values of fresh vegetables that are in high demand and also the ease of cultivation and utilization. This finding agrees with that of (Mathews-Njoku 2008; Umar *et al.* (2018) who reported that vegetables form majority of the crops cultivated in gardens, which sustains the households.

Table 6: What trees/plants can you cultivate at home?

Perception	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Moringa</i> and vegetables	44	73.33
Fruit trees	10	16.67
Papaya, mango and Indian almond	5	8.33
Others	1	1.67
Total	60	100

Source: field work 2023

CONCLUSION

This study examined the perceptions of women regarding home garden agroforestry practices in Nassarawa Local Government Area, Nigeria. The findings revealed that despite the potential benefits of home garden agroforestry, the majority of women in the study area are not engaged in the practice due to constraints such as lack of space. However, a significant proportion of women expressed willingness to participate in home garden agroforestry, indicating a potential for increased adoption and benefits. The study highlights the importance of addressing socio-cultural and environmental factors to promote women's participation in home garden agroforestry, ultimately contributing to sustainable development, food security, and women's empowerment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Provide training and capacity building: Government agencies, NGOs, and extension services should provide training and capacity-building programs for women on home garden agroforestry practices, focusing on skills such as planning, planting, and management.
2. Improve access to land and resources: Efforts should be made to improve women's access to land, credit facilities, and other resources necessary for home garden agroforestry.
3. Promote women's empowerment: Programs aimed at promoting women's empowerment, such as literacy programs, should be integrated with home garden agroforestry initiatives to enhance women's participation and benefits.
4. Develop context-specific policies: Policies and programs should be developed to address the specific needs and constraints of women in the study area, taking into account cultural, social, and environmental factors.
5. Encourage community involvement: Community-based initiatives should be encouraged to promote home garden agroforestry, involving women's groups, community leaders, and other stakeholders to ensure sustainability and scalability.
6. Conduct further research: Further research should be conducted to explore the potential benefits and challenges of home garden agroforestry in different contexts, including urban and rural areas, to inform policy and practice.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors have declared that they have no competing interests.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

Aminu conceived and designed the project, collected the data, and drafted the manuscript, Danturai supervised the research and reviewed the manuscript, the remaining authors critically evaluated and revised the manuscript, giving their final approval.

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